

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

STUDY OF GENETIC DIVERSITY OF GLOBULIN PROTEINS IN COMMON BEAN (*PHASEOLUS VULGARIS* L.) GENOTYPES

Mammadova Sh.,
Nasrullayeva M.,
Kalbiyeva Y.,
Isgandarova R.,
Huseynova T.

MSE ar genetic resources institute,
Baku, Azerbaijan

ABSTRACT

Electrophoretic analysis of globulin storage proteins was performed in the seeds of 15 introduced common bean samples in the study. The goal was identifying, passportizing, and studying the genetic diversity of common bean genotypes. Moreover, the genetic diversity index (H) was calculated in zones (ω -, γ - β - and α -) according to the frequency of occurrence of patterns in the electrophoregrams of globulin storage proteins in the seeds of common bean samples. 16 spectra and 21 patterns were detected in common bean samples, and polymorphism was observed in most of them. 4 spectra and 5 patterns, 4 spectra and 4 patterns, 4 spectra and 5 patterns, and 4 spectra and 7 patterns were observed in the ω , γ , β , α zones, respectively. The genetic diversity index was calculated based on Nei's formula for each of the 4 zones - ω , γ , β , and α . According to calculations, more genetic diversity was observed in ω -zone ($H=0.993$), slightly less in β zone ($H=0.707$), α ($H=0.837$), and least in γ zone ($H=0.580$). Genotypes were divided into 4 groups based on cluster analysis. Based on the obtained results, electrophoretic analysis of globulin storage proteins was performed for the first time in polyacrylamide gel (A-PAGE) and polymorphism was found in common bean genotypes.

Keywords: common bean, genotype, seed, globulin, storage protein, gene, pattern, electrophoregram, cluster.

INTRODUCTION

Common bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) is one of the most important legumes used as a food crop in the world. This plant is cultivated mainly in temperate regions, and is widespread in Asia and South America, mostly in developing countries [1]. Common bean has been planted and cultivated in Azerbaijan since ancient times. Common beans, which are legumes, are used as food by humans and animals. In terms of sown area, it ranks third after peas and lentils [2].

The common beans also enrich the soil with nutrients by moving nutrients from the subsoil to the topsoil through their strong root system. Common beans meet a large part of their nitrogen needs by using free nitrogen from the air through *Rhizobium phaseoli* bacteria, which live a symbiotic lifestyle, and enrich the soil with nitrogen. Common beans have high adaptability, and there are enough cultivated areas of them in our country. Each region with different climatic conditions has its own cultivation characteristics and some difficulties. However, the goal is to obtain high-quality and large-quantity crops.

The common bean (*Phaseolus* L.) belongs to the legume family, the genus Leguminosae, and it was given this name because its fruits resemble a boat. The number of chromosomes in beans is $2n=22$. Among the legumes, the most cultivated common bean plant is native to Mexico, Guatemala, Colombia, and Central and South American countries. There are 230 species of beans, 17 of which grow wild [3].

Common beans are heat-tolerant, their seeds germinate at 8-10°C. But the most favourable temperature for this plant is 18-20°C. Bean sprouts are destroyed at a temperature of 0.5-1.0°C. It should also be noted that

the seeds of its different species and varieties require different amounts of heat to germinate. Ex: 6-8°C for broad beans, 8-10°C for mung beans, 6-10°C for common beans, and 12-14°C for lima beans. A temperature of -20°C is needed to germinate fast-growing common bean varieties. Black bean seeds germinate at 2-3°C lower temperature than the white ones. Bean sprouts cannot withstand prolonged low temperatures and die at -0.5°C frost, older plants can withstand frosts down to -4°C. The optimum temperature for the flowering of common beans is considered to be 20-25°C, but depending on the species and form, it is possible for the plant to flower at a temperature of 15-40°C, and at a temperature higher than 41°C, the flowers fall. A sharp change in temperature during the growing season reduces the productivity of most varieties of beans (mainly in the tillering stage). Bean varieties imported from Asia (small beans) develop normally under high-temperature and produce well [4].

Common beans need to be in an area that receives full sunlight, especially when the plants are young, when there is no light, the plants are exposed to elongation, which results in lower yields. Long-lasting shade or cloudy weather has a devastating effect on common beans. Types and varieties of beans do not have the same relationship to the length of the day. Some varieties bloom late and bear fruit even on long days.

Common beans are food crops with high nutritional value that can be stored for a long time without changing their content. 100 g of common beans contains 0 cholesterol, 336 calories, 59.4 g carbohydrates, 23.1 g protein, 1.7 g fat, 163 mg calcium, 437 mg phosphorus, 6.9 mg iron, 0.57 mg B₁, 0.52 mg B₂, 2.5 mg.

vitamins PP (niacin)[5]. Common beans are a legume that is not inferior to red meat in terms of vegetable protein and fiber and is very rich in protein and mineral salts that help strengthen bones[6].

The amount of storage proteins in common bean seeds is highly variable due to the quantitative nature of the genes that regulate protein synthesis[7]. In general, the seeds of leguminous plants contain 20-35% albumins, 43-55% globulins, 0.73-2.70% prolamins, and 11.84-32.21% glutelins. [8]. Albumin and globulin together make up 63-90% of total proteins. The saline soluble fraction (globulins) makes up 45-50.3% of the total mass. Soluble proteins with an average value of 47.7% make up the main protein fraction [9].

Differences in molecular weights of protein bands by using SDS polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis as reported by Gupta, different variants of seed proteins viz., globulins, glutelins, albumins, and prolamins were observed in different variants. Polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (SDS-PAGE) was used for protein separation [10] and SRAP was used to evaluate legumes [11, 12, 13].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

15 introduced common bean samples were used in the study. 15 samples were sown at the Absheron Experimental Base of the Institute of Genetic Resources of ANAS, field experiments were carried out in the second and third ten days of November.

Electrophoretic analysis of globulin protein was carried out at the "Biochemical genetics and technology" department of the Institute of Genetic Resources of ANAS. Extraction and electrophoretic analysis of globulin storage proteins in common bean samples were modified in polyacrylamide gel (Acid-PAGE) by F.A. Poperelya et al. (1989) [14] and performed based on the method of W. Bushuk and R. Zilman (1978) [15].

After crushing, common bean seeds were extracted 2 times with 500 μ l of 70% alcohol, each time centrifuged at 3500 rpm, then washed 2 times with 500

μ l of 0.03% vinegar and acetone solution and centrifuged at 3500 rpm each time after dissolving with a mechanical stirrer. 500 μ l of 9 molar acetic-urea solution was added to the extract obtained after the fourth time and analyzed in a vertical electrophoresis apparatus in glycine-acetate buffer (pH-3.5).

Patterns were numbered by comparing them with each other in each zone and then numbering all patterns without taking into account repetitions. Thus, if a certain pattern is repeated in the samples, a new number is not assigned to this pattern, and all patterns are recognized according to this rule. The frequency of occurrence of each pattern of lentil samples was calculated by the following formula based on Nei's genetic diversity index in all zones.

$$H = 1 - \sum P_i^2$$

H - genetic diversity index; P_i - frequency of each pattern in the zones.

Cluster analysis was constructed by applying the UPGMA method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Protein markers are one of the main markers used in the genetic identification of plants. For the first time in Azerbaijan, the electropherograms of globulin proteins obtained during the vertical electrophoretic analysis of leguminous plants carried out by a new method by modifying the A-PAGE method were conventionally divided into 4 zones: these are called ω -, γ -, β -, and α -globulins. High-molecular-mass proteins are localized in the ω -zone and low-molecular-weight proteins are localized in the α -zone. The globulin proteins in the grains of the bean samples were relatively less polymorphic, while those of the lentil plant were more polymorphic and their spectra were intense. However, globulin proteins differed dramatically according to the polymorphism of gliadin and gluten storage proteins in wheat grain. (Figure 1).

Figure 1: The results of electrophoresis of globulin storage proteins in common bean genotype 1-K-37, 2-AzePHA-t/16, 3-AzePHA-t/17, 4-AzePHA-t/18, 5-Saksa, 6-AzePHA-18, 7-K-15274, 8-AzePHA-14, 9-Galibiyet, 10-K-3498, 11-K-13038, 12-Afgo-27, 13-AzePHA-t/6, 14- AzePHA-t/15, 15-Yerli piyada.

The spectra (bands) observed in the studied common bean genotypes were distributed in 4 zones: ω , γ , β , α zones, depending on the molecular mass of globulins and the speed of movement in polyacrylamide gels. As a result of the electrophoresis analysis of globulin storage proteins, 16 spectra and 21 patterns were detected in all zones in 15 common bean genotypes, 4 spectra in each zone, and a larger number of their combinations (7 patterns) were observed in the α zone.

4 different spectra (bands) were detected in the ω zone. Of these, spectrum No. 3 was observed in 12 samples with a frequency of 80%, on the contrary, spectra No. 1, 2, and 4 were detected in 5 samples (33.3%), 2 samples (13.3%), and 6 samples (40%), respectively. It should be noted that among the globulin zones of the studied genotypes, the highest genetic diversity ($H=0.993$) belongs to the ω zone.

Table 1.

Frequency of occurrence of patterns and spectra in common bean genotypes

Zones	(ω)		(γ)		(β)		(α)	
Number of patterns and spectra	Frequency of patterns, %	Frequency of spectra, %	Frequency of patterns, %	Frequency of spectra, %	Frequency of patterns, %	Frequency of spectra, %	Frequency of patterns, %	Frequency of spectra, %
1	20	33.3	60	93.3	33.3	20	27	73.3
2	20	13.3	13.5	86.6	7	93.3	20	20
3	20	80	7	80	13.5	100	13.5	20
4	14	40	20	100	40	46.6	13.5	66.6
5	27				7		7	
6							13.5	
7							7	

5 different patterns were found in the ω -zone (table 1), their ideogram is depicted in Figure 2. When looking at the pattern diversity of the ω -zone, it is known that the frequency of occurrence of pattern No.

4 was 14% in two genotypes, the frequency of occurrence of patterns No. 1, 2, 3 was 20%, each in three genotypes, and the frequency of occurrence of pattern No. 5 was 27% in four genotypes.

Figure 2. Ideogram of patterns observed in the ω -zone of globulin storage proteins.

Figure 3. Ideogram of patterns observed in the γ zone of globulin storage proteins.

4 spectra and 4 different patterns were detected in the γ -zone of globulin storage proteins. Among the observed spectra, spectrum No. 4 found in 15 genotypes was evaluated as a high-frequency spectrum (frequency of occurrence 100%). Spectrum No. 1 was characterized by a high-frequency (93.3%) in 14 samples, spectrum No. 2 by a medium frequency (86.6%), and spectrum No. 3 by a low frequency (80%) in 12 samples (table).

The ideogram of the patterns detected in the γ -zone of globulin storage proteins is shown in figure 6.9. Pattern No. 1 in 9 samples (60%), pattern No. 2 in 2 samples (13.5%), pattern No. 3 in 1 sample (6.6%), and pattern No. 4 in 3 samples (20%) were recorded. The

value of Nei's genetic diversity index calculated on the basis of the frequencies of occurrence of patterns observed in the γ -zone of globulin storage proteins, was 0.580, which indicates a high genetic diversity of the studied genotypes.

4 spectra and 5 patterns were observed in the β zone of globulins of 15 studied common bean genotypes. Of them, spectrum No. 2 (in 14 samples) and spectrum No. 3 (in 15 samples) were detected with a higher frequency (93.3% and 100%), spectrum No. 4 was observed (in 7 samples) with a medium frequency (46.6%), the lowest frequency was found in spectrum No.1 (in 3 genotypes) (20%).

Figure 4. Ideogram of patterns observed in the β -zone of globulin storage proteins.

Patterns No. 1 and 4 were detected with a high frequency in 33.3-40% of samples, pattern No. 3 was detected with a medium frequency in 13.5% of samples, and patterns No. 2 and 5 were found in 1 genotype.

Ideograms of 5 patterns found in the β -zone of globulin storage proteins are given in figure 6.10. The value of Nei's genetic diversity index calculated for the β -zone was 0.707.

4 spectra and 7 patterns were detected in the α -zone, spectrum No. 1, which had a high frequency of

occurrence, was found in 11 samples (73.3%), and spectra No. 2 and 3 were each found in 3 samples (20%, low), and spectrum No. 4 was found in 10 samples (66.6%, medium). Each of patterns No. 5 and 7 in the α -zone was unique and specific for only one genotype. The fact that the patterns are specific for each genotype serves to distinguish them from each other and plays a very important role in the identification and passportization of the samples. Patterns No. 3, 4, and 6 were each recorded in 2 samples, and patterns No. 1 and 2 were

recorded in 4 genotypes (27%) and 3 genotypes (20%), respectively. The value of Nei's genetic diversity index calculated for the α -zone was 0.837. The ideogram of

patterns detected in the α -zone of globulin storage proteins is shown in figure 5.

Figure 5. Ideogram of patterns observed in the α -zone of globulin storage proteins.

In order to determine the genetic distances between common bean genotypes, a cluster analysis was carried out using the UPGMA method in the study, and a graph of the genotypes was depicted using a dendrogram (Fig. 6.). Based on polymorphism of globulin

storage proteins, Jaccard genetic similarity indexes between genotypes were determined, 15 studied common bean genotypes were grouped in 4 clusters.

Figure 6. Grouping of common bean genotypes based on globulin storage proteins

The first cluster included K-13038, Aze PHA-t/6, Aze PHA 18, Saksa, yerli piyada, Aze PHA-t/16, k-15274, K-37 genotypes (8 samples). Pattern No. 4 in the ω -zone united the genotypes of K-13038, Aze PHA-t/6, Aze PHA -18, Saksa, while pattern No. 1 in the γ -zone united the genotypes of Yerli Piyada, Aze PHA-t/16, k-15274, K-37. Within this cluster, AFQO-2027 and Aze PHA-t/15; and Aze PHA-18 and Aze PHA-14 were genetically closer, and Nei's genetic distance between them amounted to 0.195. Yerli Piyada and AzePHA-t/18 were determined to be genetically distant and more different genotypes from each other (Nei's genetic distance index was 0.494). Also, AFQO-2027 and K-13038 genotypes were found to be quite different at a genetic distance amounted to 0.438.

1 genotype (K-3498) was placed in the second cluster. As a result of the analysis of the patterns, it was found that pattern No. 1 found in the β -zone distinguished this sample from other genotypes. The value of Nei's genetic distance index of the sample of Galibiyet with other samples was 0.67.

There were 4 samples (AzePHA-t/17, Aze PHA-t/18, Afqo, AzePHA-14 genotypes) in the third cluster. The samples grouped in this cluster were united by pattern No. 3 in the α -zone, as well as Aze PHA-t/17, Aze PHA-t/18 samples were united by pattern No. 2 in the β -zone, and Afqo and AzePHA-14 samples were united by pattern No. 1 in the ω -zone. In the current group, the genotypes were genetically similar (Nei's genetic distance index was 0.137), Aze PHA-t/17 and Aze PHA-t/18 genotypes (Nei's genetic distance index between them was 0.255).

The fourth cluster included 2 samples (Galibiyet and AzePNA-t/15). These samples were characterized by pattern No. 2 located in the ω -globulin zone. The smallest genetic distance in this group was 0.348.

References

1. FAO, Crops Productions, 2018. <http://www.fao.org/faostat>.
2. Lazarao A., Villar B., Aceituno-Mata L., Tardio J., De la Rosa L. The Sierra Norte of Madrid: an agrobiodiversity refuge for common bean landraces. *Genet. Resour. Crop Evol.*, 2013, v.60, p.1641-1654
3. Practical Vegetable Cultivation 7. Green Bean Cultivation. Ankara University Press, 2010, p8 (in Turkish)
4. Kaya E., Dashgan H.Y. Screening of bean genotypes concerning tolerance to drought and salinity stresses at the early plant development stage. *Ch.U. Journal of Science and Engineering Sciences*, 2013, V.29(2), pp.39-48 (in Turkish)
5. VandenLangenberg K.M., Bethke P.C., and

Nienhuis J. Patterns of fructose, glucose, and sucrose accumulation in snap and dry bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) Pods. *HortScience*, 2012, v.47 (7), p.874–878

6. John K.M., Luthria D. Amino acid, organic acid, and sugar profiles of 3 dry bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris* L.) varieties. *J. Food Sci.*, 2015, V.80 (12), p.2662–2669

7. Kumar, S., Gupta, P., Choukri, H., and Siddique, K. H. M. (2020). "Efficient breeding of pulse crops" in *Accelerated Plant Breeding. Vol. 3*. eds. S. S. Gosal, and S. H. Wani (Cham: Springer International Publishing), 1–30

8. Tchiagam, J.B.N., Bell, J.M., Nassourou, A.M., Njintang, N.Y., Youmbi, E., 2011. Genetic analysis of seed proteins contents in cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp.). *Afr. J. Biotechnol.* 10 (16), 3077-3086

9. Salem S. Alghamdi, Muhammed A. Khan, Hussein M. Migdadi, Ehab H. El-Harty, Muhammed Afzal, Muhammad Farooq "Biochemical and molecular characterization of cowpea landraces using seed storage proteins and SRAP marker patterns" *Saudi Journal of Biological Sciences* Volume 26, Issue 1. January 2019, pages 74-82

10. Gupta, P., Singh, R., Malhotra, S., Boora, K.S., Singal, H.R., 2014. Cowpea seed proteins: heterogeneity in total proteins and protein fractions. *Legume Res. Int. J.* 37 (1), 62-67

11. Alghamdi, S., Al-Faifi S., Migdadi, H., Khan, M., EL-Harty, E., Ammar, M., 2012, Molecular diversity assessment using sequence related amplified polymorphism (SRAP) markers in *Vicia faba* L. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 13, 16457-16471

12. Alghamdi, S.S., Al-Shameri A.M., Migdadi, H.M., Ammar, H.M., El-Harty, E.H., Khan, M. A., Farooq, M., 2014. Physiological and molecular characterization of faba bean (*Vicia faba* L.) genotypes for adaptation to drought stress. *J. Agro. Crop Sci.* 201 (6), 401-409

13. Rana, M., Singh, S.P., Bhat, K., 2009. Fingerprinting indian lentil (*Lens culinaris* ssp. *culinaris* Medik.) cultivars and landraces for diversity analysis using sequence-related amplified polymorphism (SRAP) markers. *Proceedings of Fourth International Food and Legumes Research Conference; New Delhi, India*, 617–624

14. Popereya F.A. //The analysis of gliadin polymorphism in wheat and their relationship between yield and quality traits // Moskva, Aqropromizdat, 1989, p. 138-149

15. W., Zillman R.R. //Wheat cultivar identification by gliadin electrophoregrams // *Can. J. Plant Sci.*, 1978, v. 58, p. 505-515